

**AI Through Gulf Students' Eyes: What They Know and
Think**

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This research dove into how aware students are of the technologies they are using, and focused on Artificial Intelligence.

This research first introduced the concept of AI and a bit of its history globally and in Gulf countries, and it then talked about one of the most important sectors that uses it, which is the educational sector.

It then goes deeper, talking about how students specifically use AI technology and what benefits they are getting from it, at the same time, what drawbacks result from this usage, and how this can be a problem for pupils, and what governments and schools are doing about this problem to find a solution to it.

After that, the method of research was described, where the data had been collected from, and what questions the students were asked.

It then shows the findings of this survey and how that even though students are aware of AI and its dangers, they are still using it due to how fast it can finish tasks and explain lessons. It also shows how schools rarely talk about AI and raise any awareness against it.

It ends with what could be done in the future to help make more students aware, which includes governments pushing schools to make activities and events for students to help increase the understanding of AI among students.

Introduction

When you hear this word, the first thing that might come to your mind is models like CHATGPT, Google Gemini, DeepSeek, etc. But in reality, AI (or known as Artificial Intelligence) is a technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision making, creativity, and autonomy (IBM,2025,What is AI?). In simpler terms, technology that gives devices the ability to mimic human qualities, like the ability to learn, solve problems, and have sentience.

While many think AI was implemented recently, in reality, the first working AI program was developed back in 1951, which was used on a Checkers-playing program developed by Christopher Strachey and a Chess-playing program developed by Dietrich Prinz. Which ran on the Ferranti Mark 1 machine of the University of Manchester.

For Gulf countries, AI was first officially treated back in 2017, when the UAE launched the UAE National AI Strategy of 2031, which aimed for the UAE to become a global leader in Artificial Intelligence by 2031 and appointed His Excellency Omar Sultan Al Olama as its minister. The UAE expects a return on investment that contributes to about 13.6% of the country's GDP by 2030

Saudi Arabia, which was soon to follow, established the SDAIA (Saudi Data and Artificial Intelligence Authority) in 2019, which oversees national agendas for data and AI. In 2020, the NSDAI (National Strategy for Data and AI) was launched by the SDAIA, aiming to make Saudi Arabia a top 15 country in AI by 2030, and attract investments that contribute to 12.4% of the country's GDP

Qatar, even though it was one of the first to begin the journey of Artificial Intelligence with the establishment of the QCRI (Qatar Computing Research Institute), it was officially proposed it when it was adopted by the Ministry of Transport in 2019, and then established the Artificial Intelligence committee with Hassan Jassim Al Sayed as chairman in 2021. Qatar's strategy identified six core pillars that continue to guide them in their development, these being: education, data access, workforce, business, research, and ethics. Their expectations are very low, as unlike the previous two, they are expecting AI to be 8.2% of the country's GDP, including other GCC countries like Kuwait, Bahrain, and Omar by 2030.

This can also be represented by the bar chart below:

A large number of AI users are in the educational sector. Students, Teachers, Principals, Parents, and other roles in a school have seen a high increase in AI usage in the last 5 years. Especially with the introduction of OpenAI's model CHATGPT, which made using AI as easy as writing prompts and getting results in seconds.

In the beginning, it was a simple asking questions and receiving answers between students and AI. Then, with the introduction of uploading files, students were able to upload their task and wait for the AI to solve each and every question.

Even though the answers were not accurate enough, many students were not aware of this fact and thought it was simply perfect, while some did know the answers had a few mistakes here and there, but were either low on time and couldn't fact-check, or just procrastinated through it and submitted it knowingly.

As much as this is a problem, a growing concern arises when students share personal or school data with AI systems, even if these platforms claim full privacy and security. Experts warn of potential privacy risks. Which is logical when you think about it,

This research is set to explore Gulf students' awareness of AI technology, their understanding of its risks, and whether schools are taking steps to raise that awareness.

Methodology

In order to find out the awareness of students about Artificial Intelligence (AI) and how they apply it in everyday learning, this study employed a quantitative method by conducting an online survey.

A Google Form survey was sent to schools and online WhatsApp communities in the Gulf region, accumulating 50 respondents. These responses were all anonymously collected and stored as a Google Sheets file, and each question was analyzed and graphed.

The questions asked were as follows:

1. Which AI do you use mainly: (i) ChatGPT, (ii) Gemini, (iii) Gro, (iv) DeepSeek (v) Copilot (vi) Other

*The questions were now asked ranging from 1(Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree)

2. I understand how AI tools work.
3. I often use AI tools to help me with schoolwork or studying,
4. AI tools have made my learning process easier and faster
5. I can tell the difference between real information and AI- AI-generated content.
6. I share personal details while talking to AI
7. My information is secure with my AI.
8. My school provides enough awareness about Artificial Intelligence and its ethical use.

Findings

With no surprise with **82%** of students use ChatGPT over other AI tools, and are followed by Other tools that haven't been mentioned in the survey were around 10% of students use them.

This can be clearly shown in the Pie Chart below:

Which AI do you use mainly?

For how well students understood AI, **most chose a 4 out of 5**, agreeing with it. It is followed by a 3 out of 5, which is a more neutral state. This is shown on the Bar chart below:

I understand how AI tools work.

50 responses

And about **38%** fully use AI to help with their school, as also shown in the table

I often use AI tools to help me with schoolwork or studying.

50 responses

below:

Many have seen time improvement while using AI. As a matter of fact, around **42%** of students fully agree that AI makes their learning faster, as shown below:

AI tools have made my learning process easier and faster.

50 responses

Now, around **36%** of students agree that they can differentiate between AI and real content, while only **2%** admitted that they can't. This can be represented like this:

I can tell the difference between real information and AI-generated content.

50 responses

Negatively, also **36%** of students disagree that they share any personal information with their AI chatbots:

I share personal details while talking to AI.

50 responses

About **8%** of students believe their data is safe with AI, while the majority of around **32%** have a neutral opinion about their data security :

My information is safe with the AI I talk to

50 responses

My school provides enough awareness about Artificial Intelligence and its ethical use.

50 responses

Lastly, **62%** of students disagreed with the awareness their schools provide:

Analysis

According to the data in the charts above, we can deduce the following:

1. ChatGPT is the most used AI tool, which can be a result of its ease of use and its impact on the internet. AI's ability to be used for almost any task, from stuff like sending WhatsApp messages to solving and producing a full PDF file of an assignment solved, is what makes students lean to it rather than any other AI tool.
2. Most students understand the concept of AI tools; they might not be able to understand deep concepts, but being able to differentiate between real and AI content shows that they are aware of what they are using and know how inaccurate it sometimes can be.
3. A lot, if not all, of students use AI technology to help them in their studies, one of its advantages being that they have seen seeing increased speed of learning and solving while using AI than the old traditional ways of searching stuff up on websites or books.
4. Students are aware of how important their data is on the internet, so they don't share any personal information with their AI agents, and have a neutral stance about whether AI companies are keeping their data encrypted or open and used by other entities.
5. Rarely has any school in the Gulf region, has batted an eye about warning their students of the uses of AI, and how dangerous it could be. Which might not be a problem now, as students are aware, but for future students and future AI tools.

Conclusion and what can be done

Gulf students have shown great adaptability to new technology and were able to leverage it to their own advantage while preventing any clear disadvantages that could cause them trouble.

And even though this research might not be 100% accurate due to people lying in the survey, it gives an overall view of where we as humans, or we as students, stand in this new revolution of AI, and how we dealt with it, and how we might be dealing with it in the future.

As governments are raising awareness about such technology, and establishing organizations that help students and adults understand such technology, and be able to use it ethically to help communities grow and develop into a more innovative environment.

Although I believe governments must push schools to introduce, at least, the basics of AI for all students, and raise awareness by making events or activities for young children. And a more detailed explanation for older students in High school to encourage the usage of AI in an ethical way, rather than to use it to laze off and decrease their learning levels.

In the end, we as humans are pushed to create and invent, that's what our nature does, and that's what we have been doing for the past centuries. Whether we use this creation is ethically or not is something decided by people who use it and how they use it. No invention is truly bad; it's the person using it unethically

References

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